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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

UNDERSTANDING AND STARTING THE COURSE

1) INTRODUCTION

To know and understand the course, the methodology, the templates and samples that the Euclid University offers, it is important for the students to understand how to work the syllabus. For me, particularly, I think that the basic introduction will guide me throughout the course and assist me to meet the requirements. To start, in this first period, I studied the materials offered at the ACA-401 Coursepack – Period 1, watched the videos, read the on-line instructions and familiarized myself with the EUCLID system. In this response paper, I will describe the main information I had access to during this process and register my comments.

2) EUCLID UNIVERSITY SYSTEM AND ESSAY WRITING: THE BASICS

The online “Euclid University” system is organized compared to the on-campus syllabus and this aids the students as they have access to the course content, allowing them to study day after day. The platform offers students the opportunity to interact with different tools. The first video gives an overview on the general structure of the course-sustainable development and diplomacy. At the same time, it gives us information about the effort to organize the syllabus on seven (7) periods and with flexible times, compared to the presential course on campus. This is an important option for students who have job schedules that include out of country missions (EUCLID 2015, 1).

It was possible to acquire information on how to advance through the course, studying one period per week and about pdf materials that will complement the students' learning. The PowerPoint video explained how to use the given materials and the different study tools. Also, it provided important tips on how to study to learn well, to prepare for quizzes and to remember important concepts to discuss during the oral examination. In the same material, information was given on how to elaborate the Response Paper (RP) as well as possible citations to be used on the Major Paper (MP). The video about ACA-401D tutorial was a very important tool to learn how to write in the style of a response paper and how we should organize this document (EUCLID 2015, 1).

The on-line page offers the option to download the templates and samples. While exploring the website we can also learn a little bit more about the course Doctorate in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (DSDD), which has a captivating syllabus (EUCLID 2015, 1). The first text *Essay Writing – The Basics* will describing below.

a) Learning about Essay Writing

The first point of this text is about how “an academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence.” The academic essay should answer a question or task. For this, it should have a thesis statement and an argument, to present or discuss something, and include relevant examples to support the thesis (EUCLID 2015, 2). One excellent paper should follow the right styles and the EUCLID Word template help us to write correctly (EUCLID 2015, 6-7).

Before starting the essay, it is very important to know that: Although there are some basic steps to writing an assignment, essay writing is not a linear process. You might work through the different stages a number of times in the course of writing an essay (EUCLID 2015, 2).

In the next section, I will present information about the steps to essay writing.

i) *Starting the Essay*

The most important thing before starting the essay is to have conscience that we need enough time to read, research, think, and write. The different types of readings of the theme can help us construct ideas, concepts, define the question and analyze. This process will help the student stablish an initial plan for the essay (EUCLID 2015, 2).

However, the job does not finish with the first version of the essay plan. The construction of this plan needs thinking, speculating, reflecting, and analyzing. Around these abilities, we need to follow the steps: 1. Analyze the task; 2. Work out the initial ideas; 3. Write an initial plan; 4. Read and research; and 5. Write a second plan (EUCLID 2015, 2).

This methodology helps to construct a more qualified essay.

ii) *Researching the Topic*

After defining the question or task of the essay theme, we enter a highly important stage. The student will need to read and research in order to get further knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and an argument to answer the essay question. To make questions about what you are reading is an opportunity to familiarize with the topic and develop ideas. In the study text (EUCLID 2015, 3), the questions suggested are:

- What do I already know about the topic?
- What do I need to read to be able to answer the essay question?
- Is this material useful to my topic/argument?
- Can I use this material to support my essay?

Another important thing in this stage is to make notes from the readings and use different tools to organize the notes and identify these in the texts.

iii) *Organizing your Ideas*

The effective phrase in this topic is “Begin organizing your research and ideas into an answer” (EUCLID 2015, 3). This is the moment when we can organize the ideas, reading the first plan and, if necessary, to draw up a second essay plan. In this stage, we can define how the essay will be structured.

iv) *Writing the Essay*

In this stage, we will write a first draft to try out the structure and framework of the essay. This will help to communicate our ideas and answer the question we formulated. The structure of an essay is composed of introduction, body, and conclusion.

The parts of the essay have features and some tips to turn the writing effective. The text *Essay Writing – The Basics* was orientated to start writing early – the earlier the better. Start with the body and work paragraph by paragraph, keep the essay question in mind, revise your first draft extensively, put the essay aside for a few days, proofread your final draft carefully, and check spelling and punctuation. It is important do not forget to “write the introduction and conclusion after the body” (EUCLID 2015, 4).

To write is an art and the inspiration comes with the ideas that are generate during the readings. In the document “Some rules of thumb for writing papers” we have some important suggestions to write the first paper. The first thing is “state the main thesis” of the paper. This should be preferably in the opening paragraph. If I don’t have a thesis, I need to get one. Another important thing is “stay focused,” “get right to the point,” “write clearly,” “do not make the writing boring and clumsy.” To repeat the same words will turn on the text boring. Moreover, we need “support assertions,” take the views we are

discussing seriously. Another important thing is when the student finish writing should read the paper out loud. Do not plagiarize. It is unacceptable (EUCLID 2015, 44).

v) *Referencing the Essay*

The references are a fundamental part of the essay. The basic text confirms, “Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence” (EUCLID 2015, 4). It is very important to check with the style of the faculty or school, which referencing system is required to be used and if it is not defined you, can use the system you are most comfortable.

Writing an essay is a process of construction where we need to put our different readings to support the discussion, the arguments, and the analysis. To construct an innovative essay based in evidence is equally challenging and motivating. At the coursepack period 1 we meet information about how to use the citations and the necessity to identify it, avoid the plagiarism. The “plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source of information”. (EUCLID 2015, 9) The consequences of plagiarism are very serious and to avoid it is to “CITE,” in-text citations or list of works cited (EUCLID 2015, 3-27).

vi) *Editing the Essay*

Editing the essay is a central part of the work. The given orientation is that once we have the well-organized and complete draft it is the moment to “1. Check the overall structure of your essay; 2. Make sure that each paragraph has a clear main point that relates to the argument; 3. Revise sentences; and 4. Check transition signals” (EUCLID 2015, 4). There are some questions, which we need to make in this stage.

Have I answered the question as directly and comprehensively as possible? Does the argument make sense? Is it balanced and well researched? Is the evidence relevant to and supportive of my argument? Have I used the consistent citation style? Have I referenced all my quotes and paraphrases? If there were any special instructions or guidelines for this assignment, have I followed them? Have I remained within the set word limit? (EUCLID 2015, 4)

To choose the style guide is essential to construct one text with “ensure consistency in your written output” (Euclid 2015, 52). Answering these questions will help us have more precision and less doubts about the essay writing. One checklist will help to hand the essay in with more security. At this course EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules – Turabian and offer to use the template that we can download and Euclid guidelines, also “recommends using American English, but both versions are obviously accepted” (EUCLID 2015, 52-77).

vii) *Handing the Essay in*

Before handing, the essay in it is very important to read, again, the assignment guidelines and to follow them. In general, one should have in mind some tips and the outcomes will be good. The text *Essay Writing* offers this advice (EUCLID 2015, 5).

3) CONCLUSION

After I studied the material, read the information course and watched the videos, it was possible to conclude and have in mind that it is very important to follow the orientation steps offered by EUCLID by the online material and course pack. One qualified essay depends on the dedication of the student to read, analyze, write and apply the structure and references.

The material that I had access to allowed me to learn about the tools needed to work during the course and I agree that practicing will give me confidence to write and construct my response paper, my master paper, the thesis and other academics documents.

I had some difficult to start the course and to organize my first Response Paper (RP) because I needed, first, to understand how to use the Euclid University platform and to understand how to study the matter and organize the documents. To have the orientation from my academic instructor was essential.

REFERENCES

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